

Final report on the Category III funded design effort on the COSIE ISS-based instrument funded under contract: 80NSSC18K0197.

Report of Work Done Under Technology Development Funds for the COSIE Instrument.

Submitted by the COSIE Team at SAO, MSFC and Co-Is

Leon Golub, Edward Deluca, Sabrina Savage, Kelly Korreck, Amy R. Winebarger, Mark Weber, Cooper Downs, Giulio del Zanna, Jenna Samra, Chad Madsen, Peter Cheimets

Introduction.

The COronal Spectrographic Imager in the EUV (COSIE) was submitted for selection in 2016 under the NASA Announcement of Opportunity NNH12ZDA006O-HPEXMO. The proposal was very highly rated and received Technology Development funds as a Category III selection, in order to address four technical areas. This report documents the successful achievement of the developments efforts in these areas.

1. The analysis tools to be used for recovering unfolded spectral intensities from overlapped slitless spectra produced in one of the two COSIE channels;
2. Demonstration of the ability to produce the high line density blazed reflection grating proposed for the COSIE spectrographic channel;
3. Risk mitigation by further refinement of the system used to point at and track the Sun over the ISS daylight orbits, including the fine-pointing system internal to the instrument. In this report, we present the results of the work done under that funding.
4. Develop the mechanism that switches the instrument channels from COSIE-C to COSIE-S.

This final report is a compendium of other reports that have been written in the process of carrying out the funded effort. There are five parts:

- Part 1: This overview section
- Part 2: The paper that we prepared on the image unfolding work
- Part 3: Discussions of the pointing control systems that were developed.
- Part 4: The effort on grating fabrication and coating
- Part 5: The design and testing work that we did on the channel selector

Each part has its own table and figure numbering, and, where applicable, its own reference section.

Science Justification

The COSIE investigation is motivated by two objectives: 1) to understand the dynamic physical processes that change closed field to open field and the reverse in the corona; 2) to understand the physical processes that control the early evolution of coronal mass ejections in the low corona. COSIE data will define the coronal structure that controls the background solar wind

conditions, and will track dynamic events out to at least $2.5 R_{\odot}$ in the high-sensitivity imaging channel, while full disk spectral reconstruction in the spectrographic channel will allow for temperature and density maps to be constructed with a cadence as fast as 30 seconds. Quick-look COSIE data are provided to the community in near real time for space weather forecast models.

Building the most sensitive EUV imager ever flown and combining it with a novel EUV reflection grating spectrograph will meet the mission objectives. COSIE utilizes the ISS infrastructure to provide a robust high duty cycle observation platform. The instrument pointing platform is based on the LASP TSIS design, currently in operation on the ISS. Standard data rates to and from the ISS are sufficient to run without lossy compression algorithms. Day/night cycles are shorter than transit times of CMEs and other eruptive events across the field of view, allowing detection of a significant sample of both slow and fast CMEs for analysis.

The COSIE investigation will address NASA goals to: 1. Understand the origin and dynamic evolution of solar plasmas and magnetic fields throughout the heliosphere; 2. Understand the plasma processes that accelerate and transport particle; 3. Improve the capability to predict the propagation and evolution of solar disturbances to enable safe travel for human and robotic exploration.

The Two Channels

Figure 1 below shows the light paths for the coronagraph (top) and the spectrograph (bottom) channels. The FOV for COSIE-C is shown in Figure 2.

Designed for extremely high throughput and with excellent imaging across a wide field-of-view (FOV), COSIE opens a new window for coronal explorations. Its design is optimized to obtain diagnostics of activity in the low corona from the disk out to beyond $2.5 R_{\odot}$, the distance at which the field is assumed to be radial in many models. Above the limb, the FOV includes the critical dynamic region that controls the origin of both the fast and slow solar wind (Habbal et al. 1997), the extended magnetic structures that can deflect coronal mass ejections (CMEs), and the region where CMEs are heated and accelerated.

In Figure 2, extended coronal structures are seen out to $3 R_{\odot}$ with a dynamic range of $\sim 10^5$ over that distance. The FOV for the Solar Dynamics Observatory (SDO) Atmospheric Imaging Assembly (AIA) (inner box) and SUVI image (outer box) are shown together with circles for 2 and 3 solar radii. The image is a composite constructed from 6 SUVI off-point images taken over ~ 1 hour, and the effective far limb exposure time is ~ 10 minutes. The higher sensitivity of COSIE will allow such images to be obtained in 1-2 seconds and will permit us to detect structures over a full $6.6 \times 6.6 R_{\odot}$ FOV at $3.1''$ resolution (Del Zanna et al. 2018).

Figure 2. A composite of seven 195 Å images taken by the SUVI instrument on NOAA’s GOES-16 from the week of Feb. 12, 2018. The AIA field of view is indicated along with the full COSIE FOV of $6.6 \times 6.6 R_{\odot}$. Streamer structure is visible out to more than $3 R_{\odot}$ (from Hurlburt et al. 2018).

Part 2: Unfolding Overlapped Slitless Imaging Spectrometer Data For Extended Sources

UNFOLDING OVERLAPPED SLITLESS IMAGING SPECTROMETER DATA FOR EXTENDED SOURCES

AMY R. WINEBARGER,¹ MARK WEBER,² CHRISTIAN BETHGE,^{1,3} COOPER DOWNS,⁴ LEON GOLUB,² EDWARD DELUCA,² SABRINA SAVAGE,¹ GIULIO DEL ZANNA,⁵ JENNA SAMRA,² CHAD MADSEN,² AFRA ASHRAF,⁶ AND COURTNEY CARTER⁷

¹NASA Marshall Space Flight Center, ST13, Huntsville, AL 35812

²Smithsonian Astrophysical Observatory, 60 Garden Street, Cambridge, MA 02138

³Universities Space Research Association, 320 Sparkman Drive, Huntsville, AL 35806, USA

⁴Predictive Science Inc., 9990 Mesa Rim Road, Suite 170, San Diego, CA 92121

⁵DAMTP, Center for Mathematical Sciences, University of Cambridge, Wilberforce Road, Cambridge, CB3 0WA, UK

⁶Barnard College, 3009 Broadway, New York, NY 10027

⁷Grinnell College, 1115 8th Ave, Grinnell, IA 50112

(Received November 15, 2018)

Submitted to ApJ

ABSTRACT

Slitless spectrometers can provide simultaneous imaging and spectral data over an extended field of view, thereby allowing rapid data acquisition for extended sources. In some instances, when the object is greatly extended or the spectral dispersion is too small, there may be locations in the focal plane where contributions from emission lines at different wavelengths contribute. It is then desirable to unfold the overlapped regions in order to isolate the contributions from the individual wavelengths. In this paper, we describe a method for such an unfolding, using an inversion technique developed for an extreme ultraviolet imaging spectrometer and coronagraph named the COronal Spectroscopic Imager in the EUV (COSIE). The COSIE spectrometer wavelength range (18.6 - 20.5 nm) contains a number of strong coronal emission lines and several density sensitive lines. We focus on optimizing the unfolding process to retrieve emission measure maps at constant temperature, maps of spectrally pure intensity in the Fe XII and Fe XIII lines and density maps based on both Fe XII and Fe XIII diagnostics.

Keywords: Sun:corona

1. INTRODUCTION

The ability to unfold spatial and spectral signals from an objective grating slitless spectroheliograph opens new windows into coronal spectroscopy. Such instruments allow for simultaneous high spectral resolution observations across the entire field of view with a single exposure. In the data from these instruments, sometimes called overlappograms, spatial and spectral information is convolved in the dispersive direction, making the interpretation of the data difficult.

There is a long history of objective grating spectroscopy in solar physics. The Naval Research Laboratory (NRL) overlappograms from the NRL S-082A spectroheliograph on *Skylab* (?) opened up the coronal EUV window for spectroscopic analysis, and demonstrated the richness of the spectral signatures for different solar features. More recently the Res-K instrument of the Russian KRONOS-I mission (?) identified 51 lines in the spectral region of 18.0 nm to 21.0 nm. Res-K was optimized to provide high separation of the spectral lines at the expense of spatial resolution in the dispersive direction. Their spectrograph images had a factor of 10 difference in the spatial resolution in the dispersive direction compared with the cross-dispersive direction. Kankelborg and collaborators (??) designed, built, and flew the Multi-Order Solar EUV Spectrograph (MOSES), a novel objective grating telescope that simultaneously captures three spectral orders of the strong He II 30.4 nm line. In their design the spatial information is captured in the zero order and the spectral information in the plus and minus one orders. Doppler shifts are easily detected in this design as the spectral displacements for the plus and minus one orders are in opposite directions.

A new instrument that makes use of objective grating spectroscopy is currently being proposed as a NASA Mission of Opportunity. It is called the “CORonal Spectroscopic Imager in the EUV: COSIE”. COSIE is a compact instrument that combines a wide field broadband EUV imager with an objective grating imaging spectrograph. COSIE is optimized for high throughput spatial imaging out to $3R_{\odot}$ and high throughput spectroscopy. COSIE data will capture global evolution and identify transient events that are difficult to capture with slit spectrographs. The COSIE wavelength range is similar to Res-K (18.6-20.5 nm), but for COSIE there is only a factor of three difference in spatial resolution between the spatial and dispersive directions ($3.1''/\text{pixel}$ vs. $9.3''/\text{pixel}$).

In this paper we apply unfolding methods developed for the MULTI-slit Solar Explorer (MUSE) mission ? to the COSIE data sets. The success of the approach for two substantially different instrumental setups is an indication of the robustness of the underlying method. From the unfolded spectra we can measure at each pixel (with sufficient signal) the emission measure distribution (i.e. the electron temperature of the plasma), spectrally pure intensities in the strong lines in the wavelength range, the electron density using line ratios from Fe XII & XIII, and a spectrum along each line of sight. We focus on the ability to unfold the data for a quiescent Sun that includes active regions and coronal holes. We defer discussion of dynamic events and regions with strong velocities to a subsequent paper. In Section 2, we describe the COSIE instrument. In Section 3, we describe the unfolding method. We validate this method using a 3D magnetohydrodynamic simulation in Section 4. In Section 5, we demonstrate this method using other data sets. In Section 6, we provide our conclusions and discuss how this technique can also be applied to other instruments.

2. COSIE DESCRIPTION

The COSIE optical system consists of a planar feed optic, spherical focus mirror, and $2k \times 2k$ backside thinned CCD detector. Light at a steep incident angle is collected by the feed optic, directed to the focus mirror, and focused onto the detector through a hole in the feed optic. The conversion from coronagraph to spectrograph is performed by flipping the feed optic, which has a mirror on one side and a diffraction grating on the other. Figure 1 shows the light paths for the coronagraph and spectrograph channels.

Figure 1. Ray trace for the two COSIE Channels: a wide-field coronagraph (left) and slitless spectrograph (right)

The passband of the instrument, defined by the reflectances of the optical surfaces and the transmissions of the filters, is nominally 18.6-20.5 nm. The off-disk coronagraph sensitivity is hundreds of times larger than the Geostationary Operational Environmental Satellite (GOES) Solar UltraViolet Imager (SUVI) and Solar Dynamics Observatory (SDO) Atmospheric Imaging Assembly (AIA) 19.3 nm channels (?). To simultaneously image both the extended corona and the disk, a partially absorbing filter is placed in the focal plane to effectively reduce the disk emission in the EUV by ≈ 200 times, allowing for 1 s exposures that include both the on and off disk coronal features. Taking into account the grating efficiency, the intensities of the individual spectral lines and the area of the grating, plus the lack of an absorbing disk in the overlappogram image, the expected exposure time for the spectrograph is also on the order of 1 s. The effective areas of the coronagraph (including the absorbing filter) and spectrograph are given in Figure 2.

UNFOLDING IMAGING SPECTROMETER DATA

Figure 2. The on-disk coronagraph effective area, with absorbing filter in place (left) and spectrograph effective area (right).

Examples of the COSIE-C and COSIE-S data products are shown in Figure 3. The N-S axis of the Sun will be oriented along the dispersion direction in COSIE-S in order to reduce overlap from multiple active regions if there are several on the disk. The field of view extends out to $3R_{\odot}$ and we expect there to be significant signal in the outer corona in the EUV (see ? for a detailed discussion.) In this paper, we focus on the inner corona where we expect the spectroheliogram signal to be strong.

Figure 3. An example of the expected COSIE data. The left panel shows the COSIE-S overlapped spectral/spatial image. The right panel shows the COSIE-C FOV shown on a SUVI wide-field mosaic.

Table 1 gives the strongest lines in the COSIE-S wavelength range for each species, the temperature of maximum emissivity, and the expected signal in the COSIE-S spectroheliogram in photons $s^{-1} line^{-1}$ for three representative cases: the quiet Sun, an active region and a flare. To obtain the line intensities we used three corresponding emission measure files as available in the CHIANTI v.8 (?) database, noting that such estimates are approximate. The strongest and brightest lines are Fe XII 19.5119 nm and Fe XIII 20.2044 nm, but there are lines from all Fe species from VIII-XIII in the COSIE-S wavelength range. These provide the basis for the expected temperature sensitivity of COSIE (primarily $5.65 \leq \text{Log } T \leq 6.25$). Outside of this temperature range on the low end is the O V 19.2906 nm line formed at $\text{Log } T = 5.35$. Additionally, there are several weaker Ca lines that can provide temperature information from $6.55 \leq \text{Log } T \leq 6.75$ for active regions. The Ca XVII 19.28 and Fe XXIV 19.204 nm resonance

Table 1. Strong Lines in the COSIE-S Wavelength Range

Ion and Wavelength (nm)	Log Maximum	Expected Signal (ph s ⁻¹ line ⁻¹)		
	Temperature	QS	AR	Flare
O V 19.2906	5.35	0.7	3.6	2116.5
O VI 18.4117	5.45	0.6	7.4	503.9
Fe VIII 18.5213	5.65	10.9	101.5	4460.3
Fe IX 18.8497	5.85	10.1	104.3	1764.1
Fe X 18.4536	6.05	18.8	234.1	2793.9
Fe XI 18.8216	6.15	30.4	577.3	6568.7
Fe XII 19.5119	6.20	30.8	1135.1	14355.0
Fe XII 18.688	6.20 ^a	8.7	304.3	3804.5
Fe XIII 20.2044	6.25	5.8	547.7	8618.1
Fe XIII 20.3826	6.25 ^a	4.0	355.3	5516.6
S XI 19.127	6.30	0.5	49.8	957.7
Ar XIV 19.4396	6.55	0.0	8.1	1131.7
Ca XIV 19.3874	6.55	0.0	20.6	3504.1
Ca XV 20.0972	6.65	0.0	13.6	4838.3
Ca XVII 19.2858	6.75	0.0	26.2	62204.1
Fe XXIV 19.204	7.25	0.0	0.0	806844.8

^aDensity-sensitive line

NOTE—The final three columns give the signal in the COSIE-S channel for three standard Chianti differential emission measures assuming a density of 10⁹ cm⁻³.

lines, the hottest in the band, become very bright during solar flares and provide information on hotter plasma. Note that the CHIANTI flare emission measure was obtained from a relatively large solar flare, a GOES class M2, during peak emission. For such large flares, short exposure times would be required to avoid saturation. This wavelength range also includes several density sensitive lines from Fe XII and Fe XIII; we include two of these in Table 1. See ? and the review of ? for additional spectral lines and diagnostics available in this wavelength range.

3. UNFOLDING METHOD

To invert the spectrometer and coronagraph data, we employ the sparse inversion method described in ? and applied to overlapping solar spectra in ?. We first cast the problem as a set of linear equations, namely

$$\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{M}\mathbf{x} \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{y} is an array that contains the COSIE S+C observational data, \mathbf{x} is an array of emission measures and \mathbf{M} is a matrix that describes how the emission measure maps into the detector for both the COSIE S+C channels. We describe \mathbf{M} for COSIE in Appendix A.

When ? applied this method to AIA data, the emission measure distribution was only a function of temperature and the data matrix was the intensity in each AIA channel in a single pixel. The returned emission measure distribution represented the emission measure along a single line of sight. For COSIE-S, however, the emission measure along a single line of sight in COSIE-C maps onto multiple detector pixels in the spectral direction. We treat each CCD row (along the dispersion direction) as an independent inversion problem. Hence, the emission measure distribution, \mathbf{x} , must at least be a distribution of both temperature and lines of sight that contribute to that row of COSIE-S data in the spectral direction. We solve for the emission measure distribution as a function of temperature (and perhaps other parameters) for all lines of sight that contribute to a single row of COSIE S+C data simultaneously. The COSIE-S channel has density sensitive spectral lines in the wavelength range, particularly from Fe XII and Fe XIII, and the COSIE resolution will be sensitive to strong (> 50 km s⁻¹) bulk flows. Hence, the emission measure distribution as a function of density and velocity can also be considered.

UNFOLDING IMAGING SPECTROMETER DATA

After establishing M , we use the LASSOLARS routine to find the best solution for the emission measure distribution for a given row of COSIE S+C data. It is a Least Angle Regression (LARS, ?) implementation of the Lasso selection method (?).

The routine is available in the Python *scikit-learn* package (?), we call it through an IDL-to-Python bridge. The underlying algorithm performs L1 regularization that minimizes both χ^2 and the complexity of the model, the latter being the sum of the emission measure values, meaning we minimize the function:

$$f = \frac{(M\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}_{obs})^2}{2n_{samples}} + \alpha \sum \mathbf{x} \quad (2)$$

where $n_{samples}$ is the number of data points. In other words, the inversion is made *sparse* by penalizing the number of parameters required to explain the data. The choice of α must be such that the data are neither under- nor overfitted by the model.

To validate the approach and determine the optimal resolutions and ranges for the inversion, we apply this method to simulated COSIE data sets. Unfortunately, there is not a single data set available that can be used to fully explore the all parameters. First we apply this method to data derived from a magnetohydrodynamic (MHD) model of the Sun; this is discussed in Section 4. For the model, the temperature and density distribution are known along every line of sight. Using this simulation, we determine the optimal spatial and temperature resolution of the inversion and demonstrate the method of determining the densities from the inverted line ratios. The MHD model has a limited temperature range of plasma. To explore how to incorporate different temperature ranges, we also apply this method to data derived from a full Sun emission measure calculation from AIA; this is discussed in Section 5. For the AIA model, the temperature distribution is known for every line of sight and there is emission at a broader range of temperatures than in the MHD model, but there is no density information. We use the optimized spatial and temperature resolution derived in Section 4 and explore how using different temperature ranges in the inversion alters the results.

4. APPLYING THE UNFOLDING METHOD TO AN MHD MODEL

One issue in solving the set of linear equations in Equation 1 comes from redundant rows in the matrix M , meaning when emission measure with different temperatures, densities, or line-of-sight (LOS) positions produce the same signature in the COSIE instrument. For instance, the COSIE-S has a nominal spatial resolution of 9.3'' in the spectral direction, though the thermal width of the spectral lines can degrade the spatial resolution even further. If we define, then, two matrix rows for lines of sight that are only 1'' apart, the resulting emission measure would produce essentially the same signal in COSIE-S. Similarly, defining a row of M for a temperature or density where COSIE has little sensitivity returns no additional information and slows down the process for solving Equation 1. The first step, then, is to determine the appropriate ranges and resolutions of the lines of sight, temperatures, and densities.

We determine these best parameters piecemeal, meaning we first consider the best spatial and temporal resolution, then include density for those values only. There are other parameters that can impact how well the set of equations can be solved that are beyond the inherent limitations of the instrument, such as the constant density or pressure we use if we are not solving for density or the elemental abundances in the emitting plasma. Below we make several different assumptions with regards to the pressure and density and defer discussion of the potential impact of the abundances to the Discussion Section.

In this section, we use a three-dimensional MHD model of the solar atmosphere, developed by Predictive Science, Inc and described briefly below. The model solution has temperature, plasma density, magnetic field strength and velocity defined at every point in the volume. None of the velocities are large enough to be resolved by COSIE-S, so for now we ignore the potential impact of the velocity on our inversion. We revisit this choice in the Discussion Section.

4.1. Description of the Model

To ensure reasonably realistic values and spatial variation of temperature and density in the solar corona, we use a high-resolution calculation by the 3D Magnetohydrodynamic Algorithm outside a Sphere (MAS) code (e.g. ???), which was used to predict the structure of the global corona during the 21 August 2017 total solar eclipse. Described in detail by ?, this calculation employed high-fidelity magnetic field observations at the inner boundary, a new Wave-Turbulence-Driven (WTD) coronal heating model (?), and a method to energize large-scale magnetic flux-systems in the low corona. Forward modeled observables, including SDO/AIA EUV images, temperature maps from DEM inversions, and broadband visible light images, compared favorably with observations, making this an ideal model to use here. The minimum and maximum temperatures of the simulation range from 0.01 to 3 MK. However, the transition region is artificially broadened to resolve the self-regulation of mass and energy in the low corona ($T_c = 0.35$ MK, see ??), and we only use temperatures above 0.4 MK in this analysis.

Based on the COSIE-C resolution and FOV, we first define a grid of lines of sight in a square that is +/- 3 solar radii from sun center at a resolution of 3.1''. We then extract the emission measure along each line of sight as a function of both density

and temperature. We fold this emission measure distribution through the COSIE response matrix and generate the simulated COSIE S+C detector images row by row. Recall that along a CCD row in the spectral dispersion direction, COSIE-C has a spatial resolution of $3.1''$ per pixel and COSIE-S has a spatial resolution of $9.3''$ per pixel.

The nominal COSIE exposure time will be 1 second, we multiply by this exposure time and then get photons pixel^{-1} . We add Poisson noise to each pixel and then average 20 noisy frames (approximately one minute of observations) together to mimic the expected data. Figure 4 shows these images for the central portion of the detector.

Figure 4. The COSIE spectroheliogram (left) and coronagraph images associated with the output of the MHD model. Only the central portion of the detector is shown. The assumed exposure time is 1 s, noise has been added and 20 images have been averaged. The Sun is oriented with North to the right in the images.

4.2. Determining the optimal spatial and temperature resolution

First, we consider only an inversion to determine the temperature distribution of the emission measure. We calculate M for constant pressures of 10^{15} and 10^{16} K cm^{-3} and constant densities of 10^8 and 10^9 cm^{-3} . As input, we use the COSIE data simulated from Predictive Science Model (see Figure 4). Note that this data includes density dependence in spectral lines even though we ignore the density dependence in this initial inversion.

We perform inversions with a temperature resolution of $\Delta \text{Log } T$ of 0.1 and 0.2. The temperature range is limited to $5.8 < \text{Log } T < 6.4$ for all of the inversions. We perform the inversions with three different spatial resolutions, Δs of $9.3''$, $18.6''$, and $27.9''$. For all of the inversions we limit the contributing FOV to ± 1.2 solar radii. This implies that the code only has the option to put emission measure in spatial bins that are Δs wide that extend to $\pm 1.2 R_{\odot}$ in the spectral (N-S) direction. The inversion code is run on each row of data independently so the final emission measure map will have a resolution of $\Delta s \times 3.1''$. Also, there is no limit on the spatial rows that can be calculated, meaning the inversion can be run on rows at distances in the E-W direction larger than $1.2 R_{\odot}$ if there is adequate signal at those distances. In this test case, we compute the inversion for 1000 rows of the CCD, which is equivalent to $\pm 1.6 R_{\odot}$ in the solar E-W direction. A description of the parameters used in this initial inversions and a summary of the results are given in Table 2. For each set of parameters, we predict the inverted COSIE data and calculate the χ^2 using the COSIE-S data. This is also given in Table 2.

The lowest values of χ^2 are associated with inversions completed with a constant density of 10^8 cm^{-3} (see runs T12 - T17). This likely reflects that the densities in the model are close to 10^8 cm^{-3} , particularly at the temperatures where there are the density sensitive lines in the COSIE wavelength range. When comparing these 6 runs, the ones with a spatial resolution of $9.3''$ (T12 and T15) have a higher χ^2 . For this reason, we discard this resolution and focus on the $18.6''$ and $27.9''$ resolutions (T13, T14, T16, T17). The χ^2 for these four inversions are essentially identical. In the interest of maintaining the highest spatial and temperature resolution possible, we choose to continue with a temperature resolution of $\Delta \text{Log } T = 0.1$ and a spatial resolution of $18.6''$.

Note these optimal resolutions are highly dependent on the COSIE instrument design. Nominally COSIE-S has $9.3''$ spatial resolution in the spectral direction, but because spectral lines are thermally broadened, this degrades the spatial resolution in the spectral direction further. The COSIE wavelength range contains spectral lines from Fe VIII - XIII, which provides excellent temperature discrimination in this temperature range.

UNFOLDING IMAGING SPECTROMETER DATA

Table 2. Summary of Inversion Parameters to Determine Temperature Maps

Run	LOS		Log Constant	Log Constant	χ^2
Number	Resolution	Δ Log T	Pressure	Density	COSIE-S
	(arcsec)		(K cm ⁻³)	cm ⁻³)	
T0	9.3	0.2	15	N/A	3.4
T1	18.6	0.2	15	N/A	2.5
T2	27.9	0.2	15	N/A	2.4
T3	9.3	0.1	15	N/A	5.1
T4	18.6	0.1	15	N/A	2.2
T5	27.9	0.1	15	N/A	2.0
T6	9.3	0.2	16	N/A	11.7
T7	18.6	0.2	16	N/A	10.3
T8	27.9	0.2	16	N/A	9.9
T9	9.3	0.1	16	N/A	11.5
T10	18.6	0.1	16	N/A	8.5
T11	27.9	0.1	16	N/A	7.8
T12	9.3	0.2	N/A	8	2.2
T13	18.6	0.2	N/A	8	0.5
T14	27.9	0.2	N/A	8	0.5
T15	9.3	0.1	N/A	8	5.0
T16	18.6	0.1	N/A	8	0.5
T17	27.9	0.1	N/A	8	0.4
T18	9.3	0.2	N/A	9	4.8
T19	18.6	0.2	N/A	9	3.8
T20	27.9	0.2	N/A	9	3.6
T21	9.3	0.1	N/A	9	6.1
T22	18.6	0.1	N/A	9	3.4
T23	27.9	0.1	N/A	9	3.1

NOTE—All calculations are made for a spatial range (N-S) of ± 1.2 solar radii and a temperature range of $5.8 \leq \text{Log T} \leq 6.4$.

4.3. Including density in the inversion

Next, we include density in the inversion, but we do not allow density to be a free parameter for all lines of sight or temperature bins. Instead we allow density to be a free parameter only for lines of sight that have greater than a specific signal in the coronagraph. We investigate how changing this cutoff impacts the inversion. Along all other lines of sight, where the coronagraph intensity is less than this cut off, we use the constant density assumption with $\text{Log } n = 10^8 \text{ cm}^{-3}$. We also apply a similar criterion for temperature. We only allow for density to be a free parameter for the $6.1 \leq \text{Log T} \leq 6.3$ temperature bins. For all other temperature bins, we use the constant density assumption. The results of the parameter study are summarized in Table 3.

Ideally, we would use the solution associated with the fewest restrictions, meaning the lowest signal in the coronagraph or Run D0 in Table 3. However, the χ^2 associated with the full Sun inversion (12.4). This is because for some rows of the inversion, we do not find an acceptable solution with this signal cutoff. These failed rows dominate the χ^2 . Fortunately, for those rows, we can simply use the solution from a different run that finds an acceptable solution. Hence we combine the inversions from all the runs into a final solution by evaluating each row of the inversion individually.

To explain, we show the χ^2 associated with three individual rows of the inversion in Figure 5. The Run Number plotted on the x-axis corresponds to the Run Number given in Table 3. The horizontal dashed line shows the minimum χ^2 for all runs for that specific row times 1.5. We assume any solution that falls below this χ^2 value is acceptable. We select the solution with the most

Table 3. Summary of Inversion Parameters to Determine Density Maps

Run Number	Signal in COSIE-C (ph s ⁻¹ pixel ⁻¹)	χ^2 COSIE-S	Number of Rows in Combined Data	
D0	100	4.5	749	
D1	200	5.6	177	
D2	300	1.5	56	
D3	400	0.9	19	
	Combined		0.3	NA

NOTE—All calculations are made for a spatial range of ± 1.2 solar radii, a LOS resolution of $18.6''$, a temperature range of $5.8 \leq \text{Log T} \leq 6.4$, and a temperature resolution of $\Delta \text{Log T} = 0.1$. The density is only allowed to vary in LOS positions where the signal in COSIE-C is greater than the value in the second column and in the temperature bins $6.1 \leq \text{Log T} \leq 6.3$. For all other LOS positions and temperature bins, we assume a constant density at 10^8 cm^{-3} . The final column gives the number of rows from each of the individual runs that go into the combined solution. The final row is the χ^2 associated with a combined data set.

free parameters (lowest run number) that meet this criterion for that row and store the emission measure distribution as a function of line of sight, temperature and density for that row in a master array. For the example row shown in the top plot, there is a high χ^2 for Run D0, but a low χ^2 for Run D1. For this row in the combined solution, we use the solution from D1. For the middle example row, all the runs have the same χ^2 so we use the solution from D0. For the bottom example row, the D0 solution has the lowest χ^2 , so we use it in the combined solution.

In this way, row by row, we build up the best estimate of the emission measure distribution for the entire field of view. The final column of Table 3 gives the number of rows of data that come from each run number. The majority of rows come from Run D0 and D1. Note the combined solution has a normalized χ^2 of 0.8. The resulting best spectrometer and coronagraph image associated with the combined data set is shown in the top panels of Figure 6. The bottom panels show a difference image between these data and the input data from the simulations shown in Figure 4.

4.4. Comparing true and inverted data

In the above subsections, we describe selecting the best parameters for the inversion. We made the selection of the best parameters based only on comparing the input and inverted spectrometer data. This is identical to how we would treat real observations as well, we would only have access to the observations to perform and evaluate the inversions. In this subsection, we compare the resulting temperature-emission measure maps, spectrally pure intensities, density maps, and spectra with those of the truth data.

Figure 7 shows the true emission measure map as a function of temperature from the Predictive Science model in the first and third columns and the inverted emission measure map in the second and fourth columns. Agreement is particularly good at temperatures that are well covered by strong lines given in Table 1.

Next we calculate the spectrally pure line intensities in the strong Fe XII and XIII lines given in Table 1, including two density sensitive lines. These comparisons are shown in Figures 8. The images show the intensity maps for the true and inverted spectral lines. The line plots show histograms of percentage error for all the pixels where more than $30 \text{ photons s}^{-1} \text{ pixel}^{-1}$ are expected. The average and standard deviation of the percentage errors are given in the histogram plots. We calculate the standard deviation of the percentage error and find that for the Fe XII 195 Å line, the standard deviation is 15%, for the Fe XII 186 Å line, the standard deviation is 35%. For the Fe XIII 202 Å line, the standard deviation is 21%, and for the Fe XIII 203 Å line, the standard deviation is 30%.

UNFOLDING IMAGING SPECTROMETER DATA

Figure 5. χ^2 for the four runs given in Table 3 for three example rows of the inversion. The horizontal dashed line shows the 1.5 times the minimum χ^2 . We assume any value of χ^2 less than this value is acceptable and choose acceptable solution with the most free parameters (the lowest run value) for that row.

We use the Fe XII and XIII line ratios to calculate the densities. We use the intensities from the true ratios and the inverted ratios. Full sun maps of the true and inverted ratios and the densities derived from them are shown in Figure 9. In these maps, we have masked the ratios and the densities where the intensity in the density sensitive line (Fe XII 186 Å or Fe XIII 203 Å) is less than 10 photons $\text{s}^{-1}\text{line}^{-1}$. [Figures with different masks levels are available in the on-line version of this article.]

In Figures 11 and 12, we show the ratios and densities in the area around the on-disk active region. In these images, we applied a mask of 1 photon $\text{s}^{-1}\text{line}^{-1}$ in the density sensitive lines. In some pixels at the edges of the active region, the ratio and density in the inverted data differ significantly from the ratio and density of the true data. In these regions, the line intensity is small. The plots on the right hand side of the figures show the percentage error of the log of the density. We show that the percentage error depends on the intensity in the density sensitive line, but in general is within 10%.

Finally, we extract the full spectra along a single line of sight and compare the true to the inverted spectra. A comparison of an active region, quiet sun, and limb spectra is shown in Figure 13.

5. APPLYING THE UNFOLDING METHOD TO AN AIA DATA SET

In the previous section, we determined the best parameters for the inversion using an MHD model. Due to the temperature limitations of the model, we were unable to apply evaluate the impact of having broader range of temperatures in the solar emitting plasma would have on the inversion. In this section, we apply the unfolding method COSIE data simulated from a full-Sun emission map derived from AIA data that spans a larger range of temperatures. We focus on how changing the range of temperatures of the inversion impacts the results.

5.1. A description of the data

Figure 6. The spectrometer and coronagraph data (top panels) associated with the best inversion scaled to the 0.5 power. The difference between these data and the input data in Figure 4 are shown in the bottom panels.

We prepared a full sun emission measure distribution as a function of position and over the range $\log T = 4.5 - 7.5$ [EMD(x, y, T)]. We started with publicly available processed AIA observations (“Level-1 data”) of the Sun on 2015-Dec-28 around 13:15 UTC. To minimize the effect of uncertainties in the solar coronal relative abundances (see e.g. ??), we restricted the dataset to the six EUV channels that are dominated by Fe lines (94 Å, 131 Å, 171 Å, 193 Å, 211 Å, and 335 Å). To reduce the number of pixels to solve, and to increase the signal-to-noise ratios, we rebinned the data to a platescale of 4.8 arcseconds. The data were deconvolved with the standard point spread functions.

For each pixel, we generated a set of EMDs of different temperature combinations, using the AIA effective areas distributed through SolarSoft together with a CHIANTI atomic model with a constant pressure of $10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-3} \text{ K}^{-1}$ and the ? coronal abundances. For many pixels, we were able to generate a set of EMDs that perfectly reconstructed the AIA data values. Where perfect solutions were not possible (due to errors in the measurements, instrument model, and/or atomic model), we generated sets of EMDs that reconstructed the AIA data to within $\chi^2 < 2.0$. To create a single representative EMD for each pixel, we eliminated members with higher emission measure weighted temperatures (i.e., $\langle T \rangle_{\text{EM}}$), and then took the mean EMD of the remaining members.

At this point, we had an EMD map of the AIA observations, binned to a platescale of 4.8 arcseconds. This map was then centrally embedded into a larger array corresponding to the larger field of view of COSIE-C. The extra pixels were initially set to zero. However, we wished to extend the corona beyond the AIA field of view in order to test the sensitivity of COSIE. In

UNFOLDING IMAGING SPECTROMETER DATA

Figure 7. The true emission measure distribution in different Log T bins 5.8-6.4 is shown in the first and third columns, the inverted EM distribution in the same temperature bins is shown in the second and fourth columns.

in addition, the performance of the unfolding might be affected by the overlapping effects of an extensive off-limb corona. To create an extended corona, the off-limb AIA corona between about 1.14 and $1.21 R_{\odot}$ was partitioned into 14 annuli. This radial range was chosen to reduce the predominance of low-lying bright features, as well as avoiding the vignetted corners of the AIA field of view. A line fit was made to the radial dropoff in $\log(\text{EMD})$. The corona beyond the AIA field of view was then filled in with random samples from the annular selected region, scaled to the radial dropoff function. Because the selected annular region

Figure 8. A comparison of the true and predicted Fe XII (top) and Fe XIII (bottom) lines. Intensity maps are scaled to the 0.5 power. The histograms reflect the percentage errors for all pixels with greater than 30 photons s^{-1} line $^{-1}$. The average and standard deviation of the percentage error is given in each line plot.

did not completely exclude coherent bright structures, the sampling produced values that appear discontinuous with the diffuse corona at the edge of the AIA field of view, but the levels are properly understood as sampling both diffuse and bright, structured off-limb corona. Thereby, in some statistical sense, the artificial halo represents the extension of both the diffuse corona and

UNFOLDING IMAGING SPECTROMETER DATA

Figure 9. The full sun ratio of the Fe XII and XIII lines from truth data and from inverted data, as well as the density determined from the ratio. A mask has been applied to the inverted ratios, and all densities setting the values to 0 if the density sensitive line is less than 10 photons $\text{s}^{-1}\text{line}^{-1}$. This image is available with other mask levels electronically. The on disk active region is shown in Figures 11 and 12.

Figure 10. Same as Figure 9 but with mask level of 1 photon $\text{s}^{-1}\text{line}^{-1}$. In the paper, this will be included in electronic version only.

bright structures (e.g., helmet streamers). For the particular analyses reported in this paper, in a final step the map was rescaled to the nominal COSIE-C platescale of 3.1 arcseconds.

Unfortunately, there remained unrealistic hot components in the EMD above $\text{Log } T$ of 6.7 where the data are poorly constrained by the AIA data. When calculating the COSIE intensities from the EMD over the entire temperature range, significant Ca XVII and Fe XXIV were present at levels that would be associated with a small solar flare, instead of an active region (see expected values in Table 1). To calculate the COSIE S+C data for this inversion, then, we use only the portion of the EMD maps below $\text{Log } T = 6.7$. The COSIE S+C data derived from this data set is shown in Figure 14. Because there is no density information in the emission measure maps, the COSIE data was calculated assuming a constant pressure of $10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-3} \text{ K}^{-1}$.

Figure 11. Fe XII active region density map for the on disk active region with $1 \text{ photon s}^{-1} \text{line}^{-1}$ mask. The true ratio and density is shown in the top panels, the inverted are shown in the bottom panels. The two plots on the right compare the true and inverted densities. The top plot shows the percentage error in the log of the density as a function of the intensity in the Fe XII 186 Å line. The bottom plot shows a normalized histogram of the percentage errors in the log of the density. The black histogram includes all pixels, the red histogram is all pixels with intensity larger than $1 \text{ photon s}^{-1} \text{line}^{-1}$, the green is $10 \text{ photons s}^{-1} \text{line}^{-1}$, and the blue $100 \text{ photons s}^{-1} \text{line}^{-1}$ in the Fe XII 186 Å line.

Figure 12. Fe XIII active region density maps. See caption for Figure 11.

5.2. Determining the best temperature range

To unfold the AIA data, we use the line of sight and temperature resolution found in Section 4, namely $18.6''$ and 0.1 . First, we consider inversions at both constant pressure and constant density and ignore density in the inversion. Details of the parameter space study are given in Table 4. We first use the temperature range used in Section 4, $5.8 \leq \text{Log } T \leq 6.4$. Those are runs A0-A3. In these runs, the lowest χ^2 is associated with a constant pressure of $10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-3} \text{ K}^{-1}$ or a constant density of 10^9 cm^{-3} . It is unsurprising that both these solutions have low χ^2 given that the data were calculated with a constant pressure assumption at

UNFOLDING IMAGING SPECTROMETER DATA

Figure 13. An example of active region, quiet sun, and limb spectra. Final article will only include active region, the other two will be available on-line only.

$10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-3} \text{ K}^{-1}$ and most of the density sensitivity in the wavelength range is at $\text{Log } T = 6.2$, which would be consistent with a constant density of $\text{Log } n = 8.8$.

Next, we run the inversion over a larger temperature range for the constant pressure of $10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-3} \text{ K}^{-1}$. The parameters used in the inversion and the χ^2 of the solutions are given in Table 4 as Runs A4-A7, with the temperature ranges considered in the second column. First we consider extending the temperature range to lower temperatures (Run A4 and A5). Recall that the COSIE wavelength range includes an O V and O VI line formed at $\text{Log } T 5.35$ and 5.45 , respectively (see Table 1), so we first

Figure 14. The COSIE spectroheliogram (left) and coronagraph images associated with the emission measure distribution derived from the AIA data. Only the central portion of the detector is shown. The assumed exposure time is 1 s and noise has been added. The Sun is oriented with North to the left of the coronagraph image.

Table 4. Summary of Runs for Temperature Maps from AIA data

Run Number	Log T Range	Constant Pressure (K cm ⁻³)	Constant Density (cm ⁻³)	χ^2 COSIE-S
A0	5.8-6.4	15	N/A	1.5
A1	5.8-6.4	16	N/A	3.0
A2	5.8-6.4	N/A	8	3.0
A3	5.8-6.4	N/A	9	1.6
A4	5.3-6.4	15	N/A	1.8
A5	5.6-6.4	15	N/A	1.7
A6	5.6-6.6	15	N/A	2.1
A7	5.6-6.8	15	N/A	2.4

NOTE—All calculations are made for a spatial range of ± 1.2 solar radii, a LOS resolution of $18.6''$, and a temperature resolution of $\Delta \text{Log T} = 0.1$.

expand the temperature range down to $\text{Log T} = 5.3$ (Run A4). However the count rates in the O lines are expected to be weak except in a solar flare and there are no additional diagnostics between the O lines and the Fe VIII line formed at $\text{Log T} = 5.65$. In Run A5, we expand the minimum temperature range to $\text{Log T} = 5.6$, which would include the temperature of peak emissivity for the stronger Fe VIII spectral line. Next we increase the maximum temperature considered in the inversion. Again, there are few spectral lines in the COSIE wavelength range that can constrain the emission measure distribution above 6.3. The Ar XIV and Ca XIV, XV and XVII lines are expected to be weak. In Runs A6-A7, we increase the maximum temperature to $\text{Log T} = 6.6$ and 6.8, respectively.

Our study finds that increasing the temperature range does not improve the normalized χ^2 . This could be due to two reasons. Because there are more free parameters, the normalization factor for the χ^2 gets smaller. Also there could be rows that do not converge to acceptable solutions. Regardless, it does not appear that increasing the temperature range improves the agreement with the data. We proceed, then, with the same temperature range used in Section 4.

UNFOLDING IMAGING SPECTROMETER DATA

Figure 15 shows the inverted spectrometer and coronagraph images (top panels) and the difference between the inverted and true data shown in Figure 14 in the bottom panels for Run A0 (temperature range of $5.8 \leq \text{Log } T \leq 6.4$). Note that the truth data includes emission measure at higher and lower temperatures than considered in the inversion. Spectral lines emitted at those higher or lower temperatures would not be present in the inverted data.

Figure 15. The COSIE spectroheliogram (left) and coronagraph images from Run A0. The bottom panels show the difference in the inverted and truth data.

Finally, we compare the truth and inverted emission measure maps in Figure 16 and Fe XII and XIII moments (Figures 17).

6. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we have demonstrated an unfolding technique for data acquired with a slitless spectrometer and imager. We have used simulated data from the proposed COSIE instrument to optimize this technique for emission measure maps at constant temperature, maps of spectrally pure intensity in the Fe XII and Fe XIII lines and density maps based on both Fe XII and Fe XIII diagnostics. For this instrument, we found that we could invert the data with a spatial resolution of $18.6''$ (two times worse than the nominal spatial resolution of the spectrometer) and a temperature resolution of $d\log t = 0.1$ over a temperature range of $5.8 \leq \text{Log } T \leq 6.4$ for a quiescent, non-flaring Sun. These parameters are closely coupled with the instrument design. One can imagine a different design that would have better or worse spatial resolution, and, if using different EUV passbands, would have sensitivity to different temperature ranges.

Figure 16. The true emission measure distribution in different Log T bins 5.8-6.4 is shown in the first and third columns, the inverted EM distribution in the same temperature bins is shown in the second and fourth columns.

The forward and inversion modelling we have used for the MHD model and the AIA dataset has been very useful to test the methods but is far from the real case. To further test and refine the modelling, we plan to work on real spectra obtained from Hinode EIS. Regarding the present models, they are largely independent of the quality of the underlying atomic data. The reliability of the present modelling for real COSIE-S data will instead of course depend not just on the accuracy but also on the completeness of the atomic data. Over the past 10 years, a series of detailed papers (see the references in ?) have shown new

UNFOLDING IMAGING SPECTROMETER DATA

Figure 17. A comparison of the true and predicted Fe XII (top) and Fe XIII (bottom) lines. Intensity maps are scaled to the 0.5 power. The histograms reflect the percentage errors for all pixels with greater than 30 photons s^{-1} line $^{-1}$. The average and standard deviation of the percentage error is given in each line plot.

atomic data calculations and new spectral lines identifications. These data have been benchmarked against the high-resolution Hinode EIS spectra, which observed the COSIE-S wavelength range. This implies that for the COSIE wavelength range, the atomic data, as made available with CHIANTI version 8 ?, are fairly complete and very accurate. In particular, the Fe XII and Fe

XIII density diagnostics available to COSIE-S are excellent ones. We are therefore confident that the present modelling will be able to provide reliable information on temperatures and densities across the whole Sun, on-disk and off-limb with unprecedented temporal cadence. The benchmark of the atomic data against the high-quality Hinode EIS spectra has also indicated that several transitions, even at such high resolution, are blended in very different ways, depending on what is observed. However, in most cases there is sufficient information in these wavelengths to deblend the lines.

As all the strongest COSIE-S lines for any solar conditions (e.g. quiet Sun, coronal holes, active regions, bright points, flares) are from Fe, the present modelling (together with the derived temperatures and densities) is largely independent of the choice of chemical abundances. However, we note that the Fe abundance does vary from solar region to region, so derived quantities such as emission measures should be treated with caution within any science analysis. As reviewed in ?, there is now considerable evidence that in the cores of active regions the Fe abundance is about a factor of 3.2 higher than its photospheric value. On the other hand, active region loops of about 1 MK have a range of values, while Fe has nearly photospheric abundances in coronal holes and most likely also in the quiet solar corona.

In this paper, we have focused on a quiescent, non-flaring Sun. COSIE is not sensitive to the magnitude of the velocities in the MHD simulation ($< 50 \text{ km s}^{-1}$) and there is of course no velocity information in the AIA dataset. In our next paper, we will use an MHD simulation of a CME eruption with much larger velocities to investigate the sensitivity of COSIE in the velocity parameter space.

One of the key aspects of the success of this inversion method is that we are able to couple the spectrometer data with the spectrally-integrated image data. The image data is able to constrain the spatial distribution of the emission, while the spectrometer data constrained the temperature and density distribution of the emission. Without the image data, we would have been far less successful.

Finally, we plan on applying this technique to other modern data sets that include data from slitless spectrometers, such as MOSES (??). Applying it to other data sets implies defining M for that instrument and performing a similar parameter space and sensitivity study that is included in this paper for COSIE. For instance, MOSES is tuned to observe the He II 30.4 nm line, with contributions from a few higher temperature lines in the passband. In that case, we would expect to not be able to constrain the emission measure as a function of temperature, but instead focus on the velocity distribution of the emission measure.

APPENDIX

A. DEFINING M FOR COSIE

M is the matrix that maps the emission measure ($EM = n^2 dz$) along a specific line-of-sight (LOS) to the Sun into detector pixels. In the COSIE spectroheliogram, emission measure along a single LOS maps into multiple pixels across the detector, while for the coronagraph, emission measure along a single LOS maps into a single (or adjacent) pixel. In this section we describe how we define and calculate M .

The COSIE detector has 2k detector pixels, n_{det} , across a row, so y is then a $[2 * n_{det}]$ matrix where the first n_{det} is the spectrometer data and the second n_{det} is the coronagraph data. The emission measure matrix, x , must be defined at whatever temperature, density, velocity, and spatial locations that contribute to the spectrometer and coronagraph data; we currently call the total number of free parameters in emission measure n_{em} and revisit shortly how these values are determined. Finally, the matrix M is $[n_{em} \times 2 * n_{det}]$, where M_{ij} describes how the emission measure with a specific line of sight, temperature, density and velocity, EM_j , maps into detector pixel i .

Each row of M is the thermally-broadened isothermal, isodense spectrum generated with spectral line emissivities from CHIANTI version 8 ? and folded with the COSIE-S+C effective areas and mapped to the appropriate detector positions for line of sight location. Figure 18 shows rows of M for several different conditions. The top panel shows how an emission measure of 10^{27} cm^{-5} from a LOS to sun center with $\text{Log T} = 6.2$ and $\text{log n} = 9.0$ maps into the detector for the spectrometer (left) and coronagraph (right). The expected intensity as a function of detector position is given in units of $\text{photons s}^{-1} \text{ pixel}^{-1}$. For the spectrometer, the wavelength array on the x-axis corresponds to the Sun center location. For the spectrometer, the response is a spectrum that contains several spectral lines, the strongest line is the Fe XII line is at 19.5 nm. For the coronagraph, the signal is confined to a single coronagraph pixel. These two responses together (S+C) constitutes one row of M . Another row of M might describe how EM from a LOS along the east limb with the same temperature and density maps into the detector, this is shown in the middle panels of Figure 18. It is essentially the same spectrum as the top panel shifted to the left. Another row of M is how EM from Sun center with $\text{Log T} = 5.8$ and $\text{Log n} = 8.0$ maps into the detector, this is shown at the bottom panels of Figure 18. Since this spectrum is at a different temperature, a different set of spectral lines is predicted.

UNFOLDING IMAGING SPECTROMETER DATA

Figure 18. The COSIE spectrometer (left) and coronagraph (right) responses for $EM = 10^{27} \text{ cm}^{-5}$ at three different values of LOS, Log T and Log n. Top panels: A LOS along Sun center with Log T = 6.2 and Log n = 9.0. Middle panels: A LOS along the east limb of the Sun with Log T = 6.2 and Log n = 9.0. Bottom panels: A LOS along Sun center with Log T = 5.8 and Log n = 8.0.

This work was supported at SAO and MSFC by NASA Grant 80NSSC18K0197 for COSIE Technology Development. CD acknowledges research support from NASA (HSR and LWS programs) and AFOSR. Computational support provided by NASAs Advanced Supercomputing Division, NSF's Texas Advanced Computing Center, and San Diego Supercomputer Center. GDZ acknowledges support from STFC (UK) via the consolidated grant to the atomic astrophysics group at DAMTP, University of Cambridge and from SAO during his visit to CfA. This material is based upon work supported by the National Science Foundation under Grant No. 1460767 that supported AA and CC during the University of Alabama-Huntsville and MSFC Research Experiences for Undergraduate program.

Part 3: Pointing System

The pointing system consists of 2 systems:

Coarse Pointing System

The Coarse Pointing System (CPS) was originally (in the 2016 proposal) designed around a system similar to what would be flown on NICER, another ISS payload. That design was based on MOOG motors, and an arrangement that was as similar to the NICER pointing system as we could make it. It required the addition of a roll system to remove the effects of the ISS's nadir pointing, that is the roll of the sun in the inertially stabilized image. After a review of all of the options, we decided to change our CPS design to one that follows the Total Solar and Spectral Irradiance System, Pointing System (TSIS Pointing System, or just plain TPS) that LASP is flying on the ISS (see Figure 1). This system is designed to be mounted on ISS and point at the Sun. Its performance is close to what we need for overall image stability. Like the NICER design, the TPS as-is does not include roll compensation. That was added during the Category III study.

Please see the Appendix for Part 3 (at the end of this section) for more details on the CPS. Please note that the animations are not included.

Figure 1: A graphic showing COSIE with the TPC system supporting it

Fine Pointing System

The second piece of the pointing system is the Fine Pointing System (FPS, see Figure 2). The CPS comes close to, but does not fully achieve, the image stability required to meet COSIE requirements for image integration times up to 10s. To compensate, we added the FPS, a tip/tilt system that rotates the instrument primary mirror about its node. This system is similar to what

we proposed in 2016 with one notable signal architecture change: the error signal that drives the tip/tilt system now comes from the same sensor that drives the CPS.

The sun sensor rides on the telescope structure, which is pointed by the CPS. Errors it measures are sent to both the CPS and the FPS. The tip/tilt stage, a much faster system than the CPS, corrects for higher frequency errors such as those driven by the ISS structure, while the CPS corrects for much lower frequency errors such as thus induced by the sun's apparent motion from the ISS orbits around the earth. The combination results in a stable image on the detector.

The tip tilt stage is an extension of a ground based stage that SAO has operated nearly continuously for the last 20 years on the SMA telescopes. Each gimbaled stage is mounted on flex-pivots. Its angle position is sensed by a Linear Variable Differential Transformer (LVDT) sensor that senses the linear displacement of the rim of the gimbal. That measurement is scaled to yield an angle. The position of each gimbal is set by linear motors.

The resulting performance prediction is shown in Figure 3. The blue line is the image motion when the system is only corrected through the CPS; it is measured directly from the TSIS sun sensor now mounted on the ISS. The periodic large errors result from the fact that the ISS is a large, extended structure that is subject to occasional large impulses. The red line shows the predicted system performance, corrected by both the CPS (in the underlying data) and the FPS (simulated performance). The large deflections are gone, at the penalty of some added high frequency, low amplitude noise. The result is an instrument with acceptable pointing stability (**required**: 3 arcsec 3- σ stability, **predicted**: 2.4 arcsec 3- σ over a period of 120 seconds).

Figure 2: The COSIE Primary Mirror supported in a 2-axis gimbals used to stabilize the COSIE image.

Figure 3: Comparison of the COSIE image stability with and without the addition of the FPS. The blue line shows the measured performance of the TPS, while the red line shows the predicted performance of COSIE with the addition of the FPS. The red line simulation starts with the data graphed in blue.

Part 4: Grating Development:

Fabrication of a grating

The COSIE flight grating is currently targeted to be a single grating, 90 mm in diameter on single crystal silicon. The period is 200 nm with a sawtooth angle of 13.25 degrees. The target resolution is 5,000. We have currently demonstrated the ability to fabricate 200 nm pitch gratings on thin silicon wafers with a 13.25 degree sawtooth. The process uses KOH to etch the sawtooth and repeated RCA-1/HF to remove any nubs from the KOH etching. The KOH mask is 30 nm of thermal oxide which is patterned via interference lithography. 100 nm of anti-reflection coating is used between the thermal oxide and photoresist for lithography. The test grating was on a 100 mm diameter wafer and patterned on a Mach-Zehnder interference lithography table.

The reflection grating is being fabricated on a silicon substrate patterned via interference lithography and etched via KOH. The silicon substrate is 150 mm diameter, ultrapure float zone, {111} crystal orientation, custom offcut at 13.25 degrees toward the {211} flat. To achieve the desired flatness, the samples are 15 mm-thick, and ground and polished. A 30 nm-thick layer of wet thermal SiO₂ is grown on the substrate to mask the KOH. The substrate is coated with an anti-reflective coating and then a positive tone photoresist, which is then exposed and developed. The pattern is transferred into the SiO₂ layer via reactive-ion etching with CF₄ and H₂. The key step is to etch a 13.25 degree sawtooth profile into the grating via KOH, masked with SiO₂. The {111} planes can be used as an etch stop in KOH since the etch rate of the non-{111} planes is ~100x faster than the {111} planes. After the sawtooth is etched, the SiO₂ mask is stripped in hydrofluoric acid. A smoothing process is added to remove any silicon left un-etched, underneath the SiO₂ mask. The process consists of roughly 10 cycles alternating between SC-1 and SC-2 (NH₄OH, H₂O₂ and H₂O heated to 80 degrees C and HF and H₂O at room temperature). After smoothing, the grating can be coated in metal to maximize x-ray reflectivity.

The COSIE-S feed-optic is a blazed 5,000 l/mm grating operating in 2nd order. The grating performance is controlled by the grating surface quality, its blaze, and the coating applied to the surface. To produce a grating with the necessary surface finish and blaze angle, we use a process of nanofabrication developed at MIT (Chang et al. 2004) with improvements described below.

The system utilizes a property of the silicon crystal that makes certain crystal faces (specifically the {111} face) selectively less reactive to potassium hydroxide (KOH). A specially prepared wafer is coated with silicon nitride, which is then ion-etched to pure silicon in a pattern that matches the designed grating period. The exposed silicon is then immersed in KOH. The silicon is etched away until it hits the {111} face. Since the wafer was initially cut such that the {111} face was tilted at the blaze angle with respect to the wafer surface, the result is a blazed grating (Figure 1). The grating can then be coated with a thin Zr layer. COSIE-S's grating is too large to fabricate in a single surface, so it will be made in two smaller sections.

We have successfully fabricated gratings of higher line count (6,200 l/mm vs. 5,000 l/mm) than required for COSIE in the Arcus effort, another SAO-led program, and we have developed the 4-dimensional alignment capability required to align the two individual grating elements onto the flat substrate. This will be tested early in Phase B in COSIE-S configuration.

Figure 1: Tilted SEM image for a sample 5000 l/mm COSIE blazed grating after 9 cycles of cyclical SC-1 (5:1:1 DI:H₂O₂:NH₄OH) and HF etching. The surface of each plane is smooth and the etch is complete.

EFFICIENCY MODELING OF THE COSIE-S GRATING COATING

In this section, we predict the optimally efficient coating configuration for the COSIE-S diffraction grating. We do so by following these steps: (1) determine the optimal material composition and thickness for the coating, (2) determine any advantages or disadvantages to using a multilayer over a single layer, and (3) determine the effects of oxidation to the coating's topmost layer.

1. Efficiency Calculation and Model Setup

We calculate grating efficiencies using *PCGrate* version 6.1 (Goray 2006). This software package uses a numerical optical integral method to determine the absolute efficiency at each diffraction order of a theoretically constructed grating. Numerical precision is largely determined by the number of collocation points applied to each boundary at regular intervals across the grating profile. The integral method is notorious for its computation costliness (e.g. Sassi & Sifaoui 2007), so *PCGrate* offers several options intended to decrease overall calculation time. However, we do not activate any of these options, which guarantees high-precision results with sufficient collocation points. To maintain reasonable computation times, we instead remove all roughness and interdiffusion at layer boundaries, arguably the most taxing feature to model with *PCGrate*.

PCGrate requires two sets of input: one describing the configuration of the modeled grating and the other describing the incident radiation field. The primary input for *PCGrate* is a modeled grating constructed from stacked, uniform layers of material, the bottommost of which is assumed to be of infinite vertical thickness. The user has near complete control over the geometric parameters defining the layers, including: vertical thickness, horizontal offset between layers, line frequency, and other parameters specific to particular profile shapes, such as the blaze angle for sawtooth profiles. Each layer is assigned a complex-valued refractive index, n , supplied by Henke et al. (1993) via the *Center for X-ray Optics* (CXRO). The secondary inputs for *PCGrate* are properties governing the incident radiation field. Within the user's control are wavelength, polarization, beam cross-section, and incidence angle.

After calculation, *PCGrate* returns absolute efficiencies for each diffraction order as well as values used to check for self-consistency. Two of these values, the condition number and the energy balance, provide information about the success of the calculation. The condition number indicates how sensitive the efficiency calculations are to initial conditions; in general, the lower the condition number, the more likely the calculation is to be accurate. The energy balance is the sum of the absorbed and reflected energy after calculation. For the purposes of this work, we take any deviation greater than 2% of the incoming energy as being an unreliable result. Although these values are exceptional indicators of unreliable calculations, they do not necessarily indicate the presence of a reliable one. The usual remedy for an unreliable result is to repeat the process with more collocation points until the condition number and the energy balance become satisfactory.

Version 6.1 of *PCGrate* allows for one input parameter to be varied during efficiency calculations. In this work, we take advantage of this feature to perform highly resolved parameter scans in vertical layer thickness, blaze angle, and wavelength.

All of the model gratings used in this work are constructed by adding features to a base grating design. The base grating consists of an infinitely thick Si substrate in vacuum with a sawtooth profile. The sawtooth frequency is a constant 5000 mm^{-1} . However, for this work, we allow the blaze angle to be freely varied.

2. Optimal Coating Material and Thickness

We calculate the 2nd-order efficiencies for gratings coated by 19 different materials commonly found in extreme ultraviolet (EUV) and x-ray optics. All tested materials are summarized in Table 1. We apply only a single-layer coating without an adhesion layer between it and the Si substrate. The grating blaze angle is initially set to 13.25° with an incidence angle of 78° with respect to the grating normal. For each material, we vary the single-layer thickness from 1 \AA to 200 \AA with a step size of 1 \AA . This test is run twice, one for TE polarization of the incident radiation and the other for TM polarization.

Table 1 – Tested Coating Materials and Their Refractive Indices

Material	Symbol	$Re(n)$ at 195.5 \AA	$Im(n)$ at 195.5 \AA
Aluminum	Al	0.9981	2.088×10^{-3}
Alumina	Al_2O_3	0.9359	4.558×10^{-2}
Gold	Au	0.8524	0.1531
Boron Carbide	B_4C	0.9236	1.576×10^{-2}
Beryllium	Be	0.9646	3.107×10^{-3}
Beryllia	BeO	0.9147	4.710×10^{-2}
Carbon	C	0.9202	2.196×10^{-2}
Chromium	Cr	0.8840	0.1124
Iridium	Ir	0.8837	0.1745
Molybdenum	Mo	0.7986	9.142×10^{-2}
Molybdenum (40%)-Ruthenium (60%) Alloy	Mo_4Ru_6	0.8148	0.1265
Platinum	Pt	0.9045	0.1648
Rhodium	Rh	0.8374	0.2244
Ruthenium	Ru	0.7876	0.1804
Silicon Monoxide	SiO	0.9570	2.279×10^{-2}
Silica	SiO_2	0.9506	2.956×10^{-2}
Tungsten	W	0.8405	0.1399
Zirconium	Zr	0.8867	1.944×10^{-2}
Zirconia	ZrO_2	0.8773	4.725×10^{-2}

Figure 2 shows the 2nd-order absolute efficiency as a function of single-layer coating thickness for all 19 materials assuming TE polarization. With the exception of the least efficient coatings, all materials produce a similar functional form: an erratic climb in efficiency within the first 50 \AA of thickness, then achieving a local maximum near 80 \AA , and finally decreasing toward an asymptotic value, although not all at the same rate. The trend is identical for TM polarization but peaking at lower efficiencies. The erratic behavior at the thin-coating limit is likely

numerical noise from the much thinner coating on the backside of the sawtooths becoming comparable to the incident wavelength. Mo, Ru, and Zr are three most efficient coatings in 2nd order around the 80 Å maximum region, each demonstrating peak efficiencies near 15% for TE polarization and 10% for TM polarization. Mo and Zr are represented well in the optical setups of recent EUV instruments, including the Mo/Si grating of the Extreme-ultraviolet Imaging Spectrometer (EIS, Culhane et al. 2007) and the Zr/Al-coated optics of the High-resolution Coronal Imager (Hi-C, Kobayashi et al. 2014). However, Ru is not well proven in practice as an effective optical coating in the EUV, likely due its extreme rarity and cost. For this reason, we will not consider it a viable candidate for the COSIE-S grating coating. Furthermore, we discount

Figure 2 – Absolute 2nd-order efficiency versus coating thickness for the 19 materials tested assuming a 13.25° blaze angle and 78° incidence with respect to grating normal. Molybdenum (dashed brown line), ruthenium (dash-dotted black line), and zirconium (dash-dotted blue line) are the three most efficient coating materials, all showing maximum efficiency around 15% at layer thicknesses near 80 Å.

Mo from our analysis since it is far less resilient than Zr against oxidation (Underwood et al. 1993), a major concern for an instrument exposed to the artificial atmosphere of the International Space Station (ISS).

The local maximum near 80 Å is likely a product of absorption and the near grazing incidence angle. For a perfect non-absorbing coating, the efficiency is expected to oscillate as the thickness increases, responding to alternating constructive and destructive interference conditions. However, the incident radiation must travel through material with $Re(n) < 1$ and a shallow angle, meaning the pathlength of a ray within a single layer is exceptionally long,

subjecting it to unusual amount of absorption. This effect is further exacerbated by increasing the coating thickness, dampening the expected in oscillations of the 2nd-order absolute efficiency.

This leaves Zr as our best candidate coating material. We continue to explore its potential by finding its optimal paired values of the blaze angle and single-layer thickness. We achieve this by assuming the original optimal value of the single-layer thickness for Zr (83 Å) and then calculating efficiencies while scanning in blaze angle from 0.25° to 45° at a step size of 0.25°. We then recalculate the efficiency, however, this time by scanning through values of thickness while assuming the optimal blaze angle. We then repeat this process, alternating between optimizing the blaze angle and the single-layer thickness, until there is no change

Figure 3 - Effects of stacked Zr/Al layer pairs on the reflectance (dot-dashed lines), the 0th-order absolute efficiency (dashed lines), and 2nd-order absolute efficiency (solid lines). The reflectance and 0th-order efficiency show marked improvements when a multilayer coating is introduced; however, the 2nd-order efficiency worsens under the same conditions.

resolved down to the step size of either value. This results in an optimal blaze angle of 15.75° at an optimal single-layer Zr thickness of 87 Å.

3. Single-layer vs. Multilayer Coatings

With the optimal single-layer Zr coating thickness known, we can now explore the effects of a multilayer configuration. Multilayers consist of alternating layers of a generally reflective material and a more transparent material. The goal is to tune the thickness of the transparent

layers to produce constructive interference at each boundary reflection, resulting in an overall improved reflectivity for the grating.

We construct a model multilayer grating by pairing Zr with Al, a pairing proven in the optical assemblies of recent EUV instruments such as Hi-C. In this setup, Al is the first layer atop the Si substrate, requiring a 60 Å Cr adhesion layer to keep it there. This addition changes the single-layer optimal thickness of Zr to 63 Å with a blaze of 15.75°. We determine the proper thickness of the Al layers by enforcing simultaneous constructive interference conditions upon pathlength difference associated with reflection at every boundary except those associated with the Cr adhesion layer. For these calculations, we account for the effects of absorption on the

Figure 4 – (a) Configuration 1 featuring a single layer of Zr allowed to freely oxidize. (b) Configuration 2 featuring a single layer of Zr capped with a topside-oxidized layer of Al. Lighter green layers have values of $Re(n)$ further below unity than darker green layers.

refraction angles and phase shifts at each boundary. This provides an Al tuning thickness of 71 Å.

To test the modeled multilayer grating, we first calculate the absolute efficiencies for a single Zr/Al pair. We then calculate the efficiencies again after adding another Zr/Al pair atop the original. We repeat this process until the grating features ten stacked Zr/Al layer pairs. The calculations are performed assuming TE polarization and the same 78° incidence angle as before.

Figure 3 shows the total reflectance, 0th-order efficiency, and 2nd-order efficiency of the grating at each step of the test. The multilayer configuration succeeds in improving the overall reflectance. However, these enhancements are not represented uniformly across all diffraction orders. Figure 3 show that the reflectance enhancements are well represented in the 0th-order nondispersive mode; however, the 2nd-order efficiency actually decreases with the increasing number of Zr/Al layer pairs. Due to this, we establish a single-layer configuration of Zr as the optimal layer configuration for the COSIE-S grating.

4. Modeling the Effects of Top-layer Oxidation

The COSIE-S grating will be exposed to oxygen-rich environments, first immediately after coating and within the artificial atmosphere of the ISS. This will subject the top coating layer of the grating to the effects of oxidation. In the case of our single-layer Zr coating, a thin film of ZrO₂ will begin to infiltrate the topmost portion of the coating. In general, Zr is

remarkably resistant to oxidation compared to other metals in Table 1. However, it still undergoes the same two-stage oxidation process as most metals: first, a rapid primary stage resulting in a protective layer of about 10 Å of ZrO₂, and second, a much slower process that adds to the original ZrO₂ over the course of years (Lyapin et al. 2004).

This leaves us with two viable configuration options: (Configuration 1) allow the single layer of Zr to oxidize as seen in Figure 4a, and (Configuration 2) cap the Zr with a largely transparent layer of Al that takes over the burden of oxidation instead, as shown in Figure 4b. Al does not oxidize as predictably as Zr, but for a partial pressure of oxygen at sea level, we expect roughly 40 Å of Al₂O₃ to form at the top (Campbell et al. 1999). For both configurations, we remove the Cr adhesion layer used in the multilayer tests and make slight optimization adjustments to the blaze angle and non-oxidized layer thicknesses. For Configuration 1, this

Figure 5 – 2nd-order absolute efficiencies across the expected COSIE-S passband for both configurations in each polarization state. Configuration 1 (black) is advantageous for TM polarization (dot-dashed lines) while Configuration 2 (red) is advantageous for TE polarization (solid lines).

results in a Zr thickness of 78 Å at a blaze angle of 16°. For Configuration 2, we have a Zr thickness of 88 Å and an Al thickness of 201 Å at a blaze angle of 15°. We then calculate the absolute efficiencies for all orders within the expected wavelength range of COSIE-S.

Figure 5 shows the results for both configurations assuming both TE and TM incident polarization states. Both configurations show comparable 2nd-order absolute efficiencies throughout; however, there are differences that promote distinct advantages for both. Configuration 1 shows a clear, linear decrease in efficiency toward the long wavelength end of

the passband in both TE and TM polarization. On the contrary, Configuration 2 shows higher efficiencies for all but the longest wavelengths, but its efficiency also falls off faster toward the long-wavelength end than Configuration 1. For TE polarization, Configuration 2 is clearly the better option. However, the advantages of Configuration 2 vanish for TM polarization where we see the same long wavelength falloff as for TE polarization but always at efficiencies below those of Configuration 1.

We must also account for practical difference between the two configurations. For Configuration 1, ZrO₂ is far more optically similar to Zr than Al₂O₃ is to Al, meaning that continued oxidation of the top layer will likely have less of an impact on Configuration 1 throughout the lifetime of COSIE. Also, the Al cap of Configuration 2 is susceptible to forming jagged crystals at the Al/Zr boundary upon application (e.g. Qadri et al. 1992), introducing boundary roughness that will drop the 2nd-order efficiency across all wavelengths. Furthermore, Al and Zr are capable of alloying via interdiffusion when deposited in stacked thin films at atmospheric conditions (Ho & Lin 1994; Voronov et al. 2011).

If we assume the incident radiation is unpolarized, the resulting 2nd-order efficiency should be the average of the TE and TM values. Considering this, Configuration 1 and Configuration 2 will produce roughly the same efficiencies across most wavelengths, with Configuration 2 having a slight advantage at shorter wavelengths. However, this is not significant enough to outweigh the structural deficiencies introduced by the Al cap. For this reason, we choose Configuration 1 as the optimal choice for the COSIE-S grating coating, producing 2nd-order efficiencies within an approximate range of 15%-20%.

REFERENCES

- Campbell, T., Kalia, R. K., Nakano, A., & Vashishta, P. 1999, *PhRvL*, 82, 4866
- Culhane, J. L., Harra, L. K., James, A. M., Al-Janabi, K., Bradley, L. J., et al. 2007, *SoPh*, 243, 19
- Goray, L. I. 2006, *NIMPA*, 536, 211
- Henke, B. L., Gullikson, E. M., & Davis, J. C. 1993, *ADNDT*, 54, 181
- Ho, J.-K., & Lin, K.-L. 1994, *JAP*, 75, 2434
- Kobayashi, K., Cirtain, J., Winebarger, A. R., Korreck, K., Golub, L., et al. 2014, *SoPh*, 289, 4393
- Lyapin, A., Jeurgens, L. P. H., Graat, P. C. J., & Mittemeijer, E. J. 2004, *JAP*, 96, 7126
- Qadri, S. B., Kim, C., Twigg, M., & Moon, D. 1992, *Surface and Coating Technologies*, 54, 335
- Sassi, I., & Sifaoui, M. S. 2007, *JOSAA*, 24, 451
- Underwood, J.H., Gullikson, E. M., Nguyen, K. 1993, *ApOpt*, 32, 6985

Voronov, D. L., Anderson, E. H., Cambie, R., Gullikson, E. M., Salmassi, F., et al. 2011, Proceedings of SPIE, 8139

Part 5: Channel Selector Mechanism

The Channel Selector Mechanism chooses which channel the COSIE instrument is operating in: with the mirror in place, the system is operating as COSIE-C (see Figure 1), with the grating in place, the system is operating as COSIE-S (see Figure 2).

Figure 1: The COSIE instrument see up in the coronagraphic channel (COSIE-C)

Figure 2: The COSIE instrument see up in the spectrographic channel (COSIE-S)

Figures 3A and 3B give a closer look at the mirror and the grating. As can be seen in Figure 3B we have reduced the size of the grating considerably from the 2016 proposal concept. This means that we can avoid assembling an overall grating by mosaicking it from smaller individual substrates. It also reduces the cost of the grating substrate, and fabrication effort considerably. Because of the brightness of the incoming light, and because this channel does not use any

additional absorbing filter over the solar disk, this still results in short image integration times (<1s).

Figure 3A and 3B: the left hand image shows the Channel selector arranged with the mirror in position, thus feeding COSIE-C, while the right hand image shows the grating in place, thus feeding COSIE-S

As part of the mechanism design, we addressed the issue of aligning the COSIE-S channel. The COSIE-C channel can be aligned in the visible. It is an imaging channel, with EUV multilayer coatings, but they have significant throughput in the visible wavelengths, and can therefore be aligned using standard techniques. This is a process that we have used on every UV and EUV telescope that we have aligned since the TRACE mission (TRACE, 4 AIA telescopes, IRIS, Hi-C 1 and 2). This is not possible for the COSIE-S channel since the visible light does not follow the EUV light off the grating. Instead we place a co-aligned visible light grating on the opposite side of the grating support plate. This provides an alignment path, and it counterbalances the grating segment (see Figure 4).

Figure 4: Showing the grating support plate with 9 cm grating segment at the top of the plate and the 4 cm visible light segment at the bottom of the plate.

Offsetting the grating from the central optical axis places an offset on the instrument focus as a function of wavelength. We place the EUV grating segment where it is shown to optimize the focus at the desired wavelength (20.4 nm), see Figure 5.

Figure 5: 10A shows the central spot size for an 18 nm beam, 10B shows a central spot for a 19.5 nm beam, and 10C shows a spot size for a 20.4 nm beam.

As part of the mechanism development effort, we prototyped the selector mechanism (See Figure 6). The goal of the prototyping effort was to test the detent portion of the mechanism. The channel selector operates by being driven from stop to stop. The position of each stop is aligned such that when it is pressed against the Stationary Permanent Magnet Stop, the optical path for the associated channel is completed. Once in position the drive motor is turned off, and the optic stage (either feed mirror or grating side active) is held in position by the attractive forces between a permanent magnet in stationary stop and an ferrous insert in the each moving stop.

We designed the test system in part to determine whether we would need to actively release the rotating stage from the stationary magnet by energizing an oppositely polarized electromagnet to momentarily counteract the effects of the permanent magnet. That is, whether the motor would be strong enough to pull the stage off the stop unassisted. Initial tests suggest that we will be able to find an optimal holding force between one that is strong enough to ensure that the rotating stage remains in position through ISS driven torque events, while weak enough to be pulled away by the drive motor.

Figure 6: Components of the COSIE Channel Selector Prototype